

ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE: ITS RAMIFICATIONS ON RETENTION OF PRODUCTION ENGINEERS IN AN ELECTRONICS COMPANY IN THE PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the perceived manifestation of various dimensions of organizational climate and their relationship to the retention of production engineers in an electronics company in the Philippines operating under a Japanese organizational setting. Specifically, the research examined the engineers' length of stay and analyzed human resource data on hiring and resignation trends within the Production Engineering Department. Employing a quantitative research design, the study utilized an adapted survey questionnaire administered to 110 engineers in the professional career band who were hired between 2000 and March 2024. The findings revealed that organizational climate, as measured by respondents' level of agreement, significantly influenced the retention decisions of production engineers to remain and work long-term in the Japanese XYZ Electronics Company. Despite the predominance of newly hired engineers within the department, the analysis of human resource data indicated consistent hiring and resignation rates across all tenure blocks. The two primary reasons cited for leaving the company were career growth opportunities and personal matters. Interestingly, the study found no statistically significant relationship between the engineers' length of stay and the organizational climate dimensions of conflict, rewards, and warmth. However, specific dimensions such as identity, support, structure, autonomy and freedom, and encouragement were identified as factors positively influencing the retention of engineers in terms of their length of stay. Based on these findings, it is recommended that engineering managers aiming to retain production engineers in a Japanese electronics company setting should implement exceptional programs and training initiatives. These should focus on strengthening organizational dimensions such as structure, identity,

support, encouragement, and autonomy and freedom to foster a conducive work environment that supports long-term retention.

Keywords: *Organizational Climate; Retention in production engineering; Japanese electronics company; Engineers in professional career band, Engineering Manager.*

INTRODUCTION

The engineers in a Production Engineering Department of Japanese XYZ Electronics Company play a critical role as innovators and core of the semiconductor industry. They are responsible for maximizing production processes, improving equipment efficiency, yield and quality, automation, program and software innovation, and machine data integration. Despite the company's strong market position and brand recognition, high turnover rates persist, and the COVID-19 pandemic has added further challenges. The opportunity for engineers, in the professional career band, to go to the company's headquarters in Japan and abroad often leads to low employee retention, as they are attracted by the higher salary and benefits offered. The Production Engineering Department, bears the brunt of attrition rate exceeding 20%. This situation incurred stress, adjustments, and increased workload for the remaining production engineers.

The production engineer retention rate, according to the recent second half of 2023 using the company's calendar (covers October 01, 2023 to March 31, 2024) in the Production Engineering Department reached less than 80% as shared by HR (Human Resources) Department. Among the available secondary data shared by HR Department, the retention was worse for Production Engineering Department compared to the 90 to 95% retention rate in other departments. The worst engineer retention was evident in the Professional Engineers career band as shared by the HR Department. Under the Production Engineering, human resources have at least 15% Middle Managers, 5% Managers, 5% Team members and 75% under the Professional Engineers Career band based on 150 Production Engineering manpower headcount in a regular employee from year 2000 until 2024.

The low retention rate among production engineers was indeed a significant concern and was deemed one of the problems the company is experiencing. It is important to explore and address the underlying factors, like the organizational climate, contributing to the low retention rate of the production engineers.

Research Questions

The main objective of this study was to evaluate the organizational climate in the Production Engineering Department of XYZ, a Japanese electronics company, and to examine the employee retention among production engineers.

1) What is the level of agreement of the production engineers to the organizational climate in a Japanese XYZ Electronics Company in terms of:

- 1.1) Autonomy and Freedom,
- 1.2) Conflict,
- 1.3) Warmth,
- 1.4) Structure,

- 1.5) Encouragement,
- 1.6) Support,
- 1.7) Identity,
- 1.8) Rewards?

The level of agreement of the production engineers to the organizational climate is the perceived manifestation of the different aspects of the eight organizational climates as listed above.

2) What is the retention of production engineers in the Production Engineering Department in XYZ Electronics Company based on length of stay and Human Resource data?

3) What is the relationship between the organizational climate and retention of production engineers in XYZ Electronics Company?

4) From an Engineering Manager's point of view, what programs could be recommended to improve the retention of production engineers in XYZ Electronics Company?

Research Significance

Understanding the aspects of the organizational climate that impact employee retention can help in adapting daily practices and developing retention programs tailored to the specific needs of engineers in a Production Engineering Department of Japanese XYZ Electronics Company

As a potential legacy project in the organization, researchers can collaborate with the management to enhance the status of the Production Engineering members and address their needs in terms of organizational climate. The findings can input information for the development of innovative strategies and retention programs based on the perspectives of production engineers and the expertise of the researcher.

Awareness about the organizational climate and its impact can inspire value-oriented actions that can lead to informed decisions that may positively influence employee retention and overall workplace dynamics.

Framework

Organizational Climate

Organizational climate can be likened to weather and climate, as it permeates the organization and influences employee behavior. Several researchers have defined organizational climate as the shared perceptions and meaning attached by employees to

the policies, practices, procedures, and behaviors they experience in their workplace (Ahmad et al., 2018; Cygler et al., 2018; Schneider et al., 2013, 2016). The organizational climate was seen by the researcher relating and interacting with the production engineer's retention.

Theoretical Perspective/s

The study was anchored on Field Theory in Social Science of Lewin (1951) which was used by Litwin and Stringer (1968) as principle to formulate the nine (9) organizational climate factors. The study of Litwin and Stringer (1968) on organizational climate was grounded in Lewin's theory, which posited that behavior is a function of both the person and the environment, thus only individuals within the organization could determine their organizational climate. In addition to providing a detailed framework on organizational climate anchored to Field Theory in Social Science of Lewin (1951), Litwin and Stringer (1968) proposed nine dimensions for the study of organizational climate which they defined as: 1. structure - the feeling that employees have about the constraints in the group, how many rules., regulations, procedures there are, is there an emphasis on "red tape" and going through channels, or is there a loose and informal atmosphere; 2. autonomy and freedom - the feeling of being your own boss, not having to double-check all your decisions, when you have a job to do, knowing that it is your job; 3. reward - the feeling of being rewarded for a job well done, emphasizing positive rewards rather than punishments, the perceived fairness of the pay and promotion policies; 4. Risk - the sense of riskiness and challenge in the job and in the organization, is there an emphasis on taking calculated risks, or is playing it safe the best way to operate; 5. warmth - the feeling of general good fellowship that prevails in the work group atmosphere, the emphasis on being well-liked, the prevalence of friendly and informal social groups; 6. support - the perceived helpfulness of the managers and other employee, emphasis on mutual support from above and below; 7. standard - the importance of implicit and explicit goal and performance standards; 8. Conflict - the feeling that managers and other workers want to hear different opinion, the emphasis placed on getting problems out in the open, rather than smoothing them over or ignoring them; 9. Identity - the feeling that you belong to a company and you are a valuable member of a working team, the importance placed on this kind of spirit.

With the Litwin and Stringer (1968) dimensions anchored to the study of Lewin's field theory, the study aimed to examine the factors that influence production engineers' decisions in Japanese XYZ Electronics Company.

Conceptual Framework

The study came up with the conceptual framework presented on Figure1. It further explains that the organizational climate as independent variable that influences the dependent variable. The dependent variable, the retention, is believed to be explained by the independent variable. The independent variable pertains to the dimension or factors used by Litwin and Stringer (1968) - (1) structure, (2) responsibility or autonomy and

freedom, (3) reward, (4) risk, (5) warmth, (6) support, (7) standard, (8) conflict, and (9) identity.

Figure1. Conceptual Framework

Philosophical Underpinnings

The study is aligned with the positivism worldview as the research paradigm. Positivism emphasizes the use of quantifiable observations and statistical analyses to draw conclusions and support or refute theories. The positivist worldview adopts an empiricist view of knowledge, asserting that knowledge is derived from human experience and can be obtained through systematic observation and measurement. It assumes that the world is composed of discrete, observable elements and events that interact in a predictable manner (Collins,2010). In this study, the positivist approach involved collecting data to test the relationship between the retention of the Production Engineer and the organizational climate factors. The aim was to gather empirical evidences that support or refute the theoretical assumptions and establish a causal relationship between the variables. Overall, the adoption of a positivist worldview aligned the study with an objective and empirical approach, enable the collection of systematic data to support or refute the proposed relationship between production engineer retention and organizational climate factors (Stephen, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design for this study involved a case study approach integrated with an adapted survey design. This case study conducted an in-depth examination of the organizational climate and the employee retention among production engineers in the Production Engineering Department of the Japanese XYZ Electronics Company by using secondary data from HR Department based on hiring date, resignation data and pick-up information gathered from exit interviews. The survey design complemented the case study approach by employing a quantitative approach to collect primary data from the production engineers. A questionnaire was utilized as the research instrument to gather data on the perceptions and experiences of the production engineers regarding the organizational climate and production engineer retention. The combination of the case study approach and survey design provided a comprehensive and holistic understanding of the organizational climate and its impact on the Production Engineer retention in the Production Engineering Department. This mixed-methods approach allowed for the triangulation of data from multiple sources, enhancing the validity and reliability of the findings.

Research Locale

110 Production Engineers in the specific professional career band hired from year 2000 until March 2024 from the Production Engineering Department of the Japanese XYZ Electronics Company answered voluntarily the survey questionnaire.

Instrument

The study involved the utilization of an adaptive-made questionnaire to assess the organizational climate and employee retention among the 110 Production Engineers in the Production Engineering Department of the Japanese XYZ Electronics Company.

Most of the questions employed a five-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral or Neither Agree nor Disagree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree). Other questions required answers in the form of information and short answers. The questions were crafted from the synthesis of the review of related literature and grounding them to the organizational climate of Kurt Lewin Field theory in Social Science (1951). The questions or survey questions were interpreted based on the definition and examples of the factors used by previous studies (Litwin & Stringer, 1968) and thus, had undergone systematic review. The questionnaire consisted of three parts. 1. Consent Form: This section obtained permission from the interviewees to use their data in the study with the option to declare anonymity if desired. 2. Organizational Climate Assessment: This section

assessed the level of agreement of the interviewees regarding the organizational climate in the Production Engineering Department of the Japanese XYZ Electronics Company.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure for the study involved the use of an adapted survey questionnaire in a production engineering point of view aligned with Litwin and Stringers definition, thus subjected to pilot testing. Prior to the data collection, the researcher sought permission from the HR Department of the Japanese XYZ Electronics Company through a letter and advised the researcher to use google forms to limit impact on daily work schedule. The online platform, specifically emails were utilized but face to face clarifications was conducted as needed.

Data Analysis

Percentages, Frequencies, Pearson R Correlation and Stepwise Regression were used to analyse and interpret the gathered data and to test the hypothesis. An intervention program was recommended based on the findings.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study did not include a cross-sectional or longitudinal study of production engineers' perceptions on the organizational climate and retention in the semiconductor industry. The samples and locale of the study were limited to production engineers in a specific professional career band in a Japanese XYZ Electronics Company located in the province of Batangas, Philippines. Therefore, the findings cannot be generalized to production engineers in the Production Engineering field in the Philippines, Japan, or other subsidiaries of the company.

Furthermore, this study only considered the top nine organizational climate extracted from the literature through a systematic review conducted by the researcher using Litwin and Stringer's (1968) organizational climate dimensions or factors.

While assessing the reliability test for the nine organizational climate factors of Litwin and Stringer (1968), one factor, Risk, acquired a low acceptance rate on Cronbach's alpha. Hence, this study considered only the eight organizational climate factors postulated by Litwin and Stringer (1968).

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

1. Level of Agreement of Engineers on the Organizational Climate in Japanese XYZ Electronics Company

1.1. *Autonomy and Freedom*

85.7% of the respondents agreed that autonomy and freedom was evident while 1.1% disagreed; 13.2% remained neutral. Managers allowed machine set-up, optimization, system improvement and process condition optimization but have concerns in terms of yield improvement activities. The Engineering Manager needs to help the Production Engineers to formulate and execute yield improvement activities. There are many situations where the Production Engineers only focus on the machine set-up, productivity, qualification, and process condition but not related to yield improvement activities. Engineers are not free to formulate and execute yield improvement activities and they are afraid that something might fail in the execution of improvement activities.

1.2 *Conflict*

64.5% of respondents agreed that conflict was managed, 11.4% disagreed, while 24.1% remained neutral. It was concluded that the engineers considerably experienced conflict management. However, concerns were not managed to be more receptive. Engineers were not satisfied on the balance between listening and talking. It would be helpful to practice mindfulness when conversing with others (Betancourt, 2023).

1.3 *Warmth*

69.5% of the respondents agreed that warmth was evident, 12.7% disagreed, while 17.7% remained neutral, while 5.5% strongly disagreed that there was a good communication between the managers and employees in the organization.

As a matter of fact, most of the respondents, agreed that they could easily relay information to their team and they could easily get feedback from their manager. Additionally, there was a good communication between managers and employees and there was a good working relationship in the organization.

1.4 *Structure*

Only 48.9% of the respondents agreed that structure was evident; 22.0% disagreed, while 29.9% remained neutral. The organization does not practice easy approval for the needed resources as findings and must consider seriously on this survey.

What looked disturbing was the number of the engineers that remained neutral. The researcher considered neutral as undecided and did not know if this organizational

climate factor of structure does exist. The results showed that the practices adopted in the organization in terms of structure was not that good, as perceived by the engineers.

1.5 Encouragement

76.4%, agreed that their supervisor shows confidence in their work group. It was also found that 74.5% of the respondents agreed that their manager encourages them to creatively solve problems on their own. A 69.1%, the lowest percentage, agreed that encouragement exists in the organization that was considerably good.

1.6 Support

72.3% of respondents agreed that support was evident in the organization; 10.7% disagreed, while 17.0% remained neutral. Most of the respondents agreed that support system was appreciated and valued. It was also found that they could always get the support from their supervisor and teammates and a free and open communication in their work group was evident. It can be concluded that the engineers experienced support although in most instances, the engineers were dealing with their Japanese counterparts with language barriers that somehow, support initiatives were affected.

1.7 Identity

56.4% of the respondents agreed that identity was evident in the organization; 21.6% disagreed, while 22.0% remained neutral. The results shows that the disagreement responses were alarming in terms of good training development plan and career growth for engineers, thus perceived as weak among the engineers. The researcher considered neutral as still undecided and did not know if this organizational climate does exist in the company.

The Manager should provide good career development programs for the professional growth of the employees. The motivation and inspiration given by the Manager to the employees can encourage them to work hard to achieve the set goals (Fountain, 2021). The engineering manager, should have a clear track, an intact succession planning and mentoring as what the engineering managers along with his co-managers experiences, specializations, and field of expertise.

1.8 Rewards

Only 34.5% of respondents agreed that rewards were evident; 36.9% disagreed, while 28.9% remained neutral. The company needs to revisit their existing reward and recognition system. The researcher considered neutral as undecided and did not know if this organizational climate factor of rewards exists in the company.

The study of Devi, et al. (2024) titled “The determinants of talent retention in the information technology services sector in Malaysia” revealed that the primary turnover reasons were dissatisfaction with salaries and limited career advancement. Findings in

the research of Kamalaveni, Ramesh, and Vetrivel (2019) showed that employers do encourage a healthy work-life balance, but to retain employees, options like reward management and the implementation and sustainable development of Industry 4.0 in Malaysia were highly dependent on IT resources, leadership, team cohesion, and external support.

2. Retention of Production Engineers in Production Engineering Department in Japanese XYZ Electronics Company based on:

Length of Stay

Production Engineers in terms of length of stay gathered from the survey results shows that there were 67 Production Engineers with 0 to 3 years of stay in the company, thus represented the 61% of the population. 17 Production Engineers have more than 10 years in the company while a total of 26 Production Engineers had stayed on the critical 3 to 10 years. The data showed that the new engineers were the vast majority, 61% of the total population of Production Engineers.

HR Data (Hiring Date and Resigned Date)

Since year 2010, hiring trend of Production Engineers was increasing to adapt to the company's capacity expansion. However, the increase in hiring also had the same increase trend on the resignation. The Japanese XYZ Electronics Company's Production Engineering Division consists of four major blocks to support production: Core, VF/SAP, Surface Finish and Back-end. There was no concentration of hiring and resigning for each block, practices and policies were assumed the same for all blocks.

HR Data on Reasons of Resignation

Based on HR Department, reasons found in the exit interview were career growth advancement and personal matter. Due to the high confidentiality for the disclosure, the HR Department opted to provide these two (2) primary reasons of leaving the company, career growth advancement and personal matter.

3. Relationship between Organizational Climate and Retention of Production Engineers in XYZ Electronics Company

Table 1 shows the summary table for Organizational climate and retention (in Length of stay) using SPSS. Out of eight (8) variables of the organizational climate, conflict rewards and warmth were found to have no significant effect on the length of stay. Warmth has significant relationship with length of stay based on Pearson R correlation. However, testing the determination if warmth has effect on length of stay, result shows have no significant effect. Interpretation does not suggest a clear viewpoint. A warmth low level of agreement shows negative correlation due to longer length of stay or a longer length of stay shows negative correlation due to warmth low level of agreement.

R square, on the other hand, as the coefficient of determination tested that the independent variable which are the organizational climate influenced the dependent variable which is the length of stay. Pearson R shows that there is a relationship between Length of stay and independent variable but the R square can determine that there is a high coefficient of determination for the Autonomy and Freedom, Structure, Encouragement, Support, and Identity that concluded that they had a significant effect on length of stay.

Based on the literature review, identity and warmth were the top considerations, but it was found in this study that only identity hit to have relationship and significant effect on length of stay. The reason may be because 61% of the respondents were new engineers and not yet meeting some of their expectations.

Interpretation of data showed negative relationship. That means that the longer the engineers stay in the company, the more reduced their level of agreement. Identity, support, structure, autonomy and freedom and encouragement were found the most important organizational climate to consider, based on the findings.

Table1. Organizational climate and retention (in length of stay) Correlation Matrix using SPSS (Summarized)

Independent Variable (IV)	Dependent Variable (DV)	CORRELATION				R Square (Coefficient of Determination)	REGRESSION	
		Pearson r Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Interpretation		p-value	Interpretation
Autonomy and Freedom	Length of Stay	-0.239	weak negative relationship	0.006	Significant relationship	0.057	0.012	IV has a significant effect on DV
Conflict		-0.070	very weak negative relationship	0.233	No significant relationship	0.005	0.466	IV has no significant effect on DV
Warmth		-0.165	very weak negative relationship	0.043	Significant relationship	0.027	0.085	IV has no significant effect on DV
Structure		-0.247	weak negative relationship	0.005	Significant relationship	0.061	0.009	IV has a significant effect on DV
Encouragement		-0.221	weak negative relationship	0.010	Significant relationship	0.049	0.020	IV has a significant effect on DV
Support		-0.298	weak negative relationship	0.001	Significant relationship	0.089	0.002	IV has a significant effect on DV
Identity		-0.310	weak negative relationship	0.000	Significant relationship	0.096	0.001	IV has a significant effect on DV
Rewards		-0.115	very weak negative relationship	0.115	No significant relationship	0.013	0.230	IV has no significant effect on DV

Over-all Assessment of Level of Agreement of Engineers on the Organizational Climate with respect to Correlation Study.

Table 2 shows the overall assessment of level of agreement of engineers on the organizational climate in a Japanese XYZ Electronics Company with respect to the Correlation Study. Five factors of organizational climate were found to have a significant effect on the length of stay and have a significant relationship based on the correlation study, namely, the autonomy and freedom, structure, encouragement, support, and identity. Structure was found to have a remarkable issue due to its high percentage of disagreement and only less than half of the engineers agreed that the structure was well considered. Identity was seemingly the same case and nearly half of the engineers agreed that the organizational climate related to identity was present. Encouragement and support, have a small disagreement but a high level of agreement. Autonomy and Freedom had a significant impact on the length of stay and the engineers have a satisfying level of agreement.

Table 2. Over-all Assessment of level of agreement on the organizational climate with respect to Correlation Study.

Organizational Climate (N=110)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)
Autonomy and Freedom	1.1	13.2	85.7
Structure	22.0	29.1	48.9
Encouragement	9.5	16.8	73.6
Support	10.7	17.0	72.3
Identity	21.6	22.0	56.4

Key Findings on the Level of Agreement of Engineers on the Organizational Climate with respect to Correlation Study

Table 3 shows the key findings on the level of agreement of the engineers on the organizational climate in Japanese XYZ Electronics Company with respect to the Correlation Study. Summarizing these key findings from previous results, the researcher obtained ideas for the needs of improvement to be considered. In Autonomy and freedom, Engineering Manager must consider the engineers freedom to formulate and execute yield improvement activities. Structure, the approval and job description, was not clearly defined. Encouragement and support were relative and needed improvement for good work modelling and open communication. There was language barrier between the Japanese and the local hindering the engineer's open communication with the administrators and encouragement from the supervisor. Lastly, identity, like structure, seemed to be a big concern as findings showed lack of good training development and career growth plan for engineers.

Table 3. Key Findings on the Level of Agreement of Engineers on the Organizational Climate

Organizational Climate	Needs Improvement
Autonomy and Freedom	Free to formulate and execute yield improvement activities.
Structure	Easy to get approval of needed resources and job description is not clearly defined
Encouragement	Supervisor serve as good work model
Support	Free and open communication relative to Initiative to help others when in need
Identity	Good training development or career growth plan

4. Recommendations for Engineering Managers

The discussion on recommendations for Engineering Managers was based on the level of agreement to the factors of structure, identity, support, encouragement, and autonomy and freedom summarized in Table 4.

Structure. Approval guidelines and procedures were a major concern, knowing that in a Japanese setting, experience is much considered, organizational structure is periodically changed every six (6) months that apparently affected the engineer's capability to ask for approvals. The Engineering Manager should focus on guiding and managing the administration to create a clear path for the approval guidelines. They should understand the organizational structure to clearly define the job description of the engineers. They may intervene using a Techno-Structural Interventions on improving the organizational effectiveness and employee performance by focusing on technology and structure of the organization like work design intervention that was believed to be capable to cover everything from redesigning job roles and individual tasks, to finding ways to automate or improve processes that impact job satisfaction. For example, individuals on a team feel stressed because they have a large workload and do not feel supported in achieving their goals. Interventions might include redesigning job specs, allocating more resources, creating reward and recognition schemes, or even improving autonomy and self-management. The Engineering Manager should have a deep understanding of the problem when considering work design interventions.

Identity. The Engineering Manager should be the one to motivate engineer on his/her value. A good training development plan and career growth for engineers should be evident and clear. Since the Engineering Manager knows the path for the career advancement of an engineer, opportunities should be always available for everyone. The Engineering Manager, also being a technical person knows the limits and boundaries and has a vast knowledge of engineering expertise should allow the engineers to apply their engineering expertise and should manage and guide the administrative side to help the team grow and advance their status quo.

Support. The Engineering Manager is the one who can motivate the engineers to support other engineers only if the Engineering Manager is a technical expert or can

identify the expert in the team to maintain the sense of balance. Each member's job or role should be understood by the Engineering Manager.

Encouragement. The Engineering Manager is the one who can motivate the engineers and the team. Engineers are technical people. They have rich knowledge when it comes to technical things, like what their managers have. In this case, the Engineering Manager has technical expertise in the same manner with the engineers. What the Engineering Manager can do is to motivate their engineers by sharing his vast experiences and help the whole team.

Autonomy and Freedom. Engineering Managers must allow their engineers to become independent and confident contributors to decision-making. They can allow the engineers to attend project meetings, provide technical inputs and perform technical jobs with less supervision. Newly hired engineers need more supervision to do the actual work, but the experienced engineers already have their expertise and skills, so they know well what they are doing. Engineering Manager should focus on the administrative and managerial stuffs that are out of their technical scope. Those project meetings, technical inputs may help the engineers achieve freedom to formulate and execute yield improvement activities. In this Japanese XYZ Electronics Company, yield improvement activities need expertise on the process, machine set-up or any technical stuff, and skills in project management to be able to formulate and execute yield improvement activities. The Engineering Manager has a big role to build this potential in the engineers.

In short, all these five factors of organizational climate are important components of Engineering management.

Table 4. Tabulated Summary of Recommendations for Engineering Manager.

Organizational Climate	Needs Improvement	Recommendations
Autonomy and Freedom	Free to formulate and execute yield improvement activities.	Level-up engineers for yield improvement activities
Structure	Easy to get approval of needed resources and job description is clearly defined	Have a clear approval guideline and work design interventions
Encouragement	Supervisor serve as good work model	Be an encouraging supervisor or Manager
Support	Free and open communication relative to Initiative to help others when in need	Create an open communication campaign program
Identity	Good training development or career growth plan	Allow application of their engineer's expertise and Manager should manage and guide the administrative side

Conclusions

Level of agreement of engineers on the organizational climate in Japanese XYZ Electronics Company

Rewards, identity, and structure were deemed important to retain engineers. Contrary to the related literatures, identity was found to be of the greatest concerns in the organization. Structure and rewards practices and policies should be reviewed to help retain the 61% Production Engineers. Perhaps the new engineers had not yet clearly understood their roles, responsibilities, and reporting structures to the company. Identity should foster a sense of belonging and value among engineers by emphasizing the organization's values and goals. Thus, recognition for their achievements and opportunities for growth and advancement are evident.

Relationship between the organizational climate and retention of the Production Engineers in XYZ Electronics Company

The study revealed that there is a significant relationship between length of stay and the eight (8) organizational climates. Identity, support, structure, autonomy and freedom and encouragement are the specific organizational climate that can significantly influence the retention of the engineers in terms of length of stay. The study also provided that the rewards, identity, and structure are important to consider in generating improvement actions and mitigating problems.

Recommendations

Recommendations for Engineering Managers who want to retain their engineers in a Japanese electronics company, should make sure and consider outstanding programs and trainings that inculcate identity, support, structure, autonomy and freedom and encouragement wherein, identity should foster the feeling that the engineers belong to a company and they are a valuable member of a working team, the managers and other employee must emphasize on mutual support from above and below; in terms of structure, rules., regulations, procedures should be clear; lastly for autonomy and freedom, managers should make their engineers feeling of being own boss, not having to double-check all their decisions.

Recommendations for the industry in a Japanese electronics company, outstanding programs that inculcates identity, support, structure, autonomy and freedom and encouragement should be evident and emphasized for their engineers to stay.

Recommendations for future research. The study used a quantitative approach while some data were collected through an open-ended questionnaire to answer “what makes you stay in the company?” Responses to this question may involve qualitative analysis that may add to the essential understanding of the organizational climate. The study can be further pursued also by considering the specific tenure, levels, field of

expertise in a company. This study has the limitation of considering only an over-all perspective within a specific career band. There can still be a difference in the considerations of new and tenured engineers in the company.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The following ethical considerations had been addressed. 1. Informed Consent: The purpose of the research was clearly explained to the respondents before proceeding with the survey. They were informed about the voluntary nature of participation and their right to withdraw at any point without consequences. 2. Data Privacy: The researcher ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the collected data. Measures were taken to protect the anonymity of the respondents and their responses. 3. Consent from the Organization: The researcher obtained permission from the HR Department before conducting the survey. 4. Retention and Disposal of Data: The identity of the respondents was securely retained for a maximum of one year to allow for any follow-up or verification, as necessary. After the specified period, all data, including any personal identifiers, would be properly disposed of to maintain confidentiality.

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